

THE EFFECTS OF PERSONALITY TRAITS ON CYBERLOAFING BEHAVIORS AND BURNOUT LEVELS OF HOTEL EMPLOYEES ON CASE OF İZMİR KONAK DISTRICT

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the effect of personality traits on employees' cyberloafing behavior and their burnout levels. The data for the research were collected from 370 employees in 4 and 5 star hotels in Konak, İzmir, using a structured questionnaire, face-to-face and online, with convenience sampling method. Data were tested with descriptive statistical methods, exploratory factor analysis and multiple linear regression analysis. As a result, it has been revealed that personality traits have an effect on cyberloafing behavior and burnout levels. In line with the results of the research, it was revealed that the neuroticism and extraversion variable had a positive effect on the significant cyberloafing behavior, while the agreeable dimension had a negative significant effect. In addition, various suggestions have been developed for researchers, hotel and human resources managers in line with the research results.

Keywords: Personality Traits; Cyberloafing Behavior; Burnout Levels; Hotel Staff.

OS EFEITOS DOS TRAÇOS DE PERSONALIDADE NOS COMPORTAMENTOS DE CIBERFUGA E NOS NÍVEIS DE ESGOTAMENTO DE FUNCIONÁRIOS DE HOTEL NO CASO DO DISTRITO DE KONAK EM İZMİR

Resumo

O objetivo deste estudo é examinar o efeito dos traços de personalidade no comportamento de cyberloafing dos funcionários e em seus níveis de burnout. Os dados para a pesquisa foram coletados de 370 funcionários em hotéis de 4 e 5 estrelas em Konak, İzmir, utilizando um questionário estruturado, presencialmente e online, com o método de amostragem por conveniência. Os dados foram testados com métodos estatísticos descritivos, análise fatorial exploratória e análise de regressão linear múltipla. Como resultado, foi revelado que os traços de personalidade têm um efeito no comportamento de cyberloafing e nos níveis de burnout. De acordo com os resultados da pesquisa, foi constatado que a variável neuroticismo e a dimensão extroversão tiveram um efeito positivo no comportamento significativo de cyberloafing, enquanto a dimensão agradável teve um efeito significativo negativo. Além disso, diversas sugestões foram desenvolvidas para pesquisadores, gerentes de hotéis e recursos humanos, em conformidade com os resultados da pesquisa.

Palavras-chave: Traços de Personalidade; Comportamento cyberloafing; Níveis de Burnout; Funcionários do hotel.

LES EFFETS DES CARACTÉRISTIQUES PERSONNELLES DES EMPLOYÉS DE L'HÔTELLERIE SUR LE COMPORTEMENT DE RELÂCHEMENT VIRTUEL ET LES NIVEAUX D'ÉPUISEMENT PROFESSIONNEL: LE CAS DU DISTRICT D'İZMİR KONAK

Resumé

L'objectif de cette étude est d'examiner l'effet des traits de personnalité sur le comportement cyberloafing des employés et leur niveau d'épuisement professionnel. Les données de la recherche ont été collectées auprès de 370 employés dans des hôtels 4 et 5 étoiles à Konak, İzmir, à l'aide d'un questionnaire structuré, en face à face et en ligne, avec une méthode d'échantillonnage de commodité. Les données ont été testées à l'aide de méthodes statistiques descriptives, d'une analyse factorielle exploratoire et d'une analyse de régression linéaire multiple. En conséquence, il a été révélé que les traits de personnalité ont un effet sur le comportement cyberloafing et les niveaux d'épuisement professionnel. Conformément aux résultats de la recherche, il a été révélé que la variable névrosisme et extraversion avait un effet positif sur le comportement significatif de cyberloafing, tandis que la dimension agréable avait un effet significatif négatif. En outre, diverses suggestions ont été développées pour les chercheurs, les responsables des hôtels et des ressources humaines en fonction des résultats de la recherche.

Mots clés: Traits de personnalité ; Comportement de cyberloafing ; Niveaux d'épuisement professionnel ; Personnel de l'hôtel.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, with technological developments, individuals have many opportunities such as online shopping, interaction with people from different cultures, financial transactions, transactions related to investments. Additionally, applications such as hyperlink, augmented reality and virtual reality have become part of tourism experiences (Damian, 2020). With the internet provider having features that will make life easier for people, individuals are becoming more and more dependent on mobile and desktop devices day by day.

Business life, which is important for individuals to continue their lives in a quality way, is also seriously affected by this situation. Although employees use the conveniences

of technology for work, sometimes this situation can also be used to meet personal needs (Gülduran & Perçin, 2020: 38).

In the literature, these personal needs are named as cyberloafing behavior, and when employees tend to this behavior, situations such as lack of time control, not fully realizing or postponing the work to be done can lead organizations to financial losses (Dede, 2018: 1).

Personality, which is an individual element, is of great importance for employees to show cyberloafing behavior (Ünal, 2019: 1). Because personality traits can encourage individuals to do a behavior and this may differ from person to person. It is possible for people to reach material, spiritual and cultural satisfaction with their physical and mental efforts in their working life (Okutan, 2010: 1).

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When employees cannot reach this satisfaction, they may experience burnout. Although this situation is especially seen during periods of high workload, it is very important to determine the factors that affect the physical or mental problems experienced by the employees in terms of the quality and continuity of the service provided (Çiçek & Aknar, 2019: 1235).

The most important of these factors is personality traits. Although different personality traits are reflected in the behaviors of the employees, the level of experiencing burnout also changes as a result of these personality traits. For the reasons stated above, this study was carried out to investigate how employee personality factors affect cyberloafing behavior and burnout levels. Within the framework of the results obtained, various suggestions were given to researchers, hotel and human resources managers.

2 THEORETICAL REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. The Relationship Between Personality Traits and Cyberloafing

Personality is a set of consistent relationships that a person establishes with his/her inner and outer environment, which includes different characteristics that distinguish the individual from other individuals (Cüceloğlu, 1991: 19). Personality is the mental, emotional, sociable and permanent features of the individual (Özdemir et al., 2012: 567).

Cyberloafing, on the other hand, is the behavior that employees do online without being aware of their managers (Askew et al., 2014). Based on these definitions, the relationship between personality traits and internet use is one of the prominent issues today (Özcan, 2019: 27). It has been revealed that the majority of behaviors related to Internet use occur as a result of personality traits (Levin & Stokes, 1986).

Today, internet use has reached the level of addiction in individuals, and it emerges as cyberloafing behavior, especially in working individuals. Even the problems that individuals experience in daily life can lead to cyberloafing behavior (Zeren & Yalçın, 2021: 113). At this point, personality traits are important. Many studies in the literature (Krishnan et al., 2010; Jia et al., 2013; Andreassen et al., 2014; Varghese & Barber, 2017; Örucü & Aksoy, 2018; Ünal, 2019) have examined the relationship between personality traits and cyberloafing behavior. In addition, Robinson & Bennet (1995) and Blanchard & Henle (2008), who were the first to classify cyberloafing, examined cyberloafing activities in two groups.

These; are serious and minor cyberloafing behaviors. Visiting sexually explicit sites, playing online gambling or games of chance during working hours are serious cyberloafing behaviors (Blanchard & Henle, 2008). Individuals who attempt serious cyberloafing behavior do so consciously and are aware of the risk (Sarica, 2020: 31). Checking e-mail addresses and interacting with others, using online shopping sites, banking transactions and browsing news sites, regardless of work, are minor cyberloafing behaviors (Blanchard & Henle, 2008).

H1: Employees' personality traits have an effect on cyberloafing behaviors.

2.1.1. The Relationship Between Openness to Experience and Serious and Minor Cyberloafing

Openness to experience dimension of personality traits is also known as "openness to development". Openness to experience is a personality dimension that expresses individuals who are more sensitive about creativity, artistry and curiosity (Çikmaz, 2020: 29). For this reason, undesirable and penal sanctions such as serious cyberloafing behavior; they will be more inclined to enter gambling sites, sexual content sites and music download sites (Case & Young, 2002: 356).

Some of the studies (Krishnan et al., 2010; Tan & Demir, 2018; Biçkes et al., 2018; Gülduran & Perçin, 2020; Sheikh et al., 2019) revealed a positive and significant relationship between openness to experience personality dimension and serious cyberloafing behavior. revealed that there is a relationship.

While individuals who are open to experience participate in social activities and are open to all kinds of ideas and thoughts (Village, 2011), it can be said that the minor cyberloafing behavior does not take this situation seriously and does not harm the business (Ayazlar et al., 2018: 27).

Most of the studies (Jia & Jia, 2015; Biçkes et al., 2018; Gülduran, 2018; Tan & Demir, 2018; Ünal, 2019) revealed that the effect of openness to experience sub-dimension on minor cyberloafing behavior is positive and significant.

H1a: The dimension of openness to experience from personality traits has a serious positive effect on cyberloafing behavior.

H1b: Openness to experience dimension from personality traits has a positive and significant effect on minor cyberloafing behavior.

2.1.2. The Relationship Between Conscientiousness and Serious and Minor Cyberloafing

Responsibility dimension is also expressed as "self-discipline". Self-discipline is defined as the degree of motivation, determination and orderliness of an individual regarding a goal (Çetin & Varoğlu, 2009: 62). Individuals who show serious cyberloafing behavior isolate themselves from their colleagues and turn to activities such as online chatting, messaging, gambling and downloading music (Koçak, 2021).

For this reason, in many studies (Dalal, 2005; Jia et al., 2013; Mark & Ganzach, 2014; Abidin et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2015; Tan & Demir, 2018) individuals with high conscientiousness scores have serious cyberloafing. appeared to be less prone to behavior. In the minor cyberloafing behavior; visiting websites with news and sports content that are not related to work, visiting online shopping sites and visiting financial sites (Özdemir & Demir, 2015: 1031).

Many studies (Lim, 2002; Tan & Demir, 2018; Jia et al., 2013; O'Neill et al., 2014; Varghese & Barber, 2017; Dede, 2018) have been conducted in the literature revealed that there is a negative relationship between them.

H1c: The dimension of conscientiousness from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on serious cyberloafing behavior.

H1d: The dimension of conscientiousness from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on minor cyberloafing behavior.

2.1.3. *The Relationship Between Neuroticism and Serious and Minor Cyberloafing*

Psychologist Eysenck expressed the dimension of neuroticism as emotional instability, emotional state and instability (Ulucan & Bahadır, 2011: 177). Neurotic individuals have low emotional balance and it can be said that they are less successful in stress management than other people (Ünüvar, 2021: 80). Some studies in the literature (Jia, 2008; Örucü & Aksoy, 2018; Varghese & Barber, 2017; Ünal, 2019; Sheikh et al., 2019) revealed a positive relationship between neuroticism and serious cyberloafing.

Neurotic individuals experience extreme sensitivity, fear, anger and insecurity in every event (Doğan, 2013: 58). Individuals who show minor cyberloafing behavior use only the areas where the internet is used and e-mail service in the business environment (Amarat et al., 2017: 106). For this reason, while the study of Çivilidağ (2017) shows that there is a positive relationship between the two dimensions, some studies (Örucü & Aksoy, 2018; Ünal, 2019) show that there is no significance between the two dimensions.

H1e: Neuroticism dimension from personality traits has a positive and significant effect on serious cyberloafing behavior.

H1f: Neuroticism dimension from personality traits has a positive and significant effect on minor cyberloafing behavior.

2.1.4. *The Relationship Between Agreeableness and Serious and Minor Cyberloafing*

Individuals with the dimension of agreeableness are helpful, forgiving, compassionate and truthful (Tatlıoğlu, 2014: 944). Individuals who show serious cyberloafing behavior may also spend a lot of time playing games and entering various betting sites, and their productivity at work may decline and become addictive (Kara & Karalar, 2021: 43).

Many studies (Dede, 2018; Gülduran & Perçin, 2020; Sheikh et al., 2019) show that individuals with agreeable personality traits tend to have less serious who tend to minor cyberloafing behavior visit personal e-mail or short-term news sites (Blanchard & Henle, 2008: 1067). For this reason, this type of behavior seems more innocent than the other. However, studies (Dede, 2018; Gülduran, 2018; Ünal, 2019) have revealed that there is a negative and weak relationship between the agreeable personality sub-dimension and minor cyberloafing behavior.

H1g: The agreeableness dimension of personality traits has a negative and significant effect on serious cyberloafing behavior.

H1h: The agreeableness dimension from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the minor cyberloafing behavior.

2.1.5. *The Relationship Between Extraversion and Serious and Minor Cyberloafing*

Extraverted people are energetic, self-confident, talkative and social people who are aggressive in the social environment, love collective environments, action and sincerity (Costa & McCrae, 1992: 65). In the study of Wyatt & Philips (2005), it was revealed that extroverted individuals are more prone to significant cyberloafing behavior by using the internet for different purposes. Studies (Krishnan et al., 2010; Jia et al., 2013; Andreassen et al., 2014; Örucü & Aksoy, 2018; Varghese & Barber, 2017; Çivilidağ, 2017; Tan & Demir, 2018) have also support this view.

Extraversion is when individuals like to talk and increase their social circle day by day (Loveland, 2004). Minor cyberloafing behavior is; It includes behaviors that can be ignored in terms of business, such as reading e-newspapers, making personal phone calls, but also should not be done at the same time (Ünal & Tekdemir, 2015: 99). Studies (Örucü & Aksoy, 2018; Gülduran, 2018; Dede, 2018; Tan & Demir, 2018; Ünal, 2019) show that extraversion has no effect on minor cyberloafing activity.

H1i: The extraversion dimension of personality traits has a positive and significant effect on serious cyberloafing behavior.

H1j: The extraversion dimension from personality traits has a positive and significant effect on minor cyberloafing behavior.

2.2. *The Relationship Between Personality Traits and Burnout Levels*

The feelings of burnout experienced by individuals in their work can vary according to their personality traits (Süren et al., 2016: 250). Many studies in the literature (Mills & Huebner, 1998; Storm & Rothman, 2003; Bakker et al., 2006; Kim et al., 2007; Miner, 2007; Knežević et al., 2007; Malak, 2009; Okutan, 2010); Kaşlı & Seymen, 2010; Zopiatis et al., 2010; Yılmaz, 2013; Gök, 2021) examined the relationship between personality traits and burnout levels.

In his article published in 1974, Freudenberger used burnout for the first time and brought this concept to the literature as "occupational hazard" (Arı & Bal, 2008: 132). Maslach and Jackson (1981) revealed that the three dimensions of burnout are emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and low personal achievement. In addition, it is stated that the most important and determining dimension of the concept of burnout is emotional exhaustion (Gülay, 2019: 6).

The depersonalization dimension is the situation where the individual stays away from people and does not participate in work life or in the environment of friends without establishing any emotional bond with them (Komala & Ganesh, 2007: 125). In the low personal achievement dimension of burnout, individuals constantly see themselves as unsuccessful and describe them negatively (Wright & Douglas, 1997: 492). Emotional exhaustion symptoms; It can show many results such as decrease in performance at work, not going to work or avoiding work, alienation from work, decrease in the quality of the work done and leaving the job (Şeker, 2019: 42).

H2: Employees' personality traits have an effect on their burnout levels.

2.2.1. *The Relationship Between Openness to Experience and Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Low Sense of Personal Accomplishment*

Individuals who are open to experience reject strict rules, do not take a situation that measures them seriously (Tekin, 2012: 126) and may experience emotional exhaustion when they experience intense work stress (Yüksel, 2017: 38). For this reason, some studies (Deary et al., 1996; Zopiatis et al., 2010; Kapusuz & Çavuş, 2018; Maylor, 2018) revealed a positive relationship between openness to experience and emotional exhaustion sub-dimension. In the dimension of depersonalization, individuals may exhibit cold attitudes by withdrawing from work and colleagues upon experiencing an event different from their own beliefs in the work environment (Gülay, 2019: 7).

Studies in the literature (Bakker et al., 2006; Okutan, 2010; Zellars et al., 2000; Süren et al., 2016; Muzika, 2019) revealed that there is a negative relationship between openness to experience and depersonalization. In addition, individuals who are open to experience will have less opportunity to experience the feeling of personal failure, since they always tend to the newest, different, original and closest to art (Çetin, 2018: 8).

Studies (Kokkinos, 2007; Süren et al., 2016; Kapusuz & Çavuş, 2018; Tanar, 2020) show that there is a negative relationship between the two dimensions, showing that individuals who are open to experience have low sense of personal accomplishment.

H2a: The dimension of openness to experience from personality traits has a positive and significant effect on the dimension of emotional exhaustion.

H2b: Openness to experience dimension from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on depersonalization dimension.

H2c: Openness to experience dimension from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on low sense of personal accomplishment.

2.2.2. *The Relationship Between Conscientiousness and Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, Low Sense of Personal Accomplishment*

Individuals with the conscientiousness personality trait create a sense of confidence in all matters, choose the path to success, and focus on organization (Costa & McCrae, 1992: 178). In emotional exhaustion, individuals experience loss of emotion, energy and desire as a result of the problems they experience (Cordes & Dougherty, 1993). For this reason, based on some studies in the literature (LePine et al., 2004; Kim et al., 2009; Kaşlı, 2009; Zopiatis et al., 2010; Dinç et al., 2013), people with high conscientiousness will experience less emotional exhaustion. and it can be said that they are more successful in managing it. People with a high depersonalization score, on the other hand, have a desire to isolate themselves from the people around them and be alone (Tilim, 2019: 26).

In this respect, as individuals' sense of

conscientiousness increases, their depersonalization scores will tend to decrease. Studies (Okutan, 2010; Zopiatis et al., 2010; Morgan & Bruin, 2010; Süren, 2015; Tanar, 2020) also support this statement. Conscientiousness individuals also have a higher sense of personal accomplishment and experience low levels of burnout (Dinç et al., 2013: 62). Some of the studies (Piedmont, 1993; Deary et al., 1996; Deary et al., 2003; Hochwalder, 2006; Kokkinos, 2007; Dinç et al., 2013) have considered this dimension of burnout as personal achievement, and revealed that there is a positive relationship between personal conscientiousness and personal achievement.

H2d: The dimension of conscientiousness from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the dimension of emotional exhaustion.

H2e: The dimension of conscientiousness from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the dimension of depersonalization.

H2f: The dimension of conscientiousness from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the dimension of low sense of personal accomplishment.

2.2.3. *The Relationship Between Neuroticism and Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Low Sense of Personal Accomplishment*

Individuals with a high rate of neuroticism are fragile and look at every event negatively by showing serious reactions to bad situations (Tanar, 2020: 46). For this reason, studies conducted in which neurotic people experience more emotional exhaustion (Deary et al., 1996; Zellars et al., 2000; Bühler & Land, 2003; Lingard, 2003; LePine et al., 2004; Bakker et al., 2006; Ghorpade et al., 2007; Kim et al., 2009; Tanar, 2020; Süren, 2015).

Neurotic individuals cannot establish emotional relationships with people, as their depersonalization increases with the symptoms they experience (Bayat & Selçuk, 2017: 4). Studies in the literature (Deary et al., 1996; Zellars, Perrew & Hochwarter, 2000; Bühler & Land, 2003; Lingard, 2003; LePine et al., 2004; Bakker et al., 2006; Okutan, 2010; Yüksel, 2017; Düz, 2015; Muzika, 2019) revealed that there is a positive relationship between neuroticism and depersonalization.

On the other hand, low personal success is when individuals are not appreciated as a result of their work and see themselves as inadequate (Duru et al., 2014). Thus, it was observed that as neuroticism increased in individuals, low sense of personal accomplishment increased as well. In studies dealing with the relationship between neuroticism and personal achievement (Deary et al., 1996; Lingard, 2003; Le pine, Le pine, & Jackson, 2004; Miner, 2007; Kokkinos, 2007; Okutan, 2010; Muzika, 2019).

H2g: The neuroticism dimension of personality traits has a positive and significant effect on the emotional exhaustion dimension.

H2h: The neuroticism dimension of personality traits has a positive and significant effect on the depersonalization dimension.

H2i: The neuroticism dimension of personality traits has a positive and significant effect on the low sense of personal accomplishment.

2.2.4. The Relationship Between Agreeableness and Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Low Sense of Personal Accomplishment

Since harmonious individuals have the ability to keep up with teamwork (Çobanoğlu, 2021: 53), they experience less emotional exhaustion, especially in business life. Studies in the literature (Piedmont, 1993; Kim et al., 2009; Kaşlı, 2009; Okutan, 2010; Zopiatis et al., 2010; Süren, 2015; Maylor, 2018; Tanar, 2020; Bahar & Köroğlu, 2021).

It shows that there is a negative relationship between agreeableness and emotional exhaustion. In individuals, reluctance, being constantly tired, and depersonalization occur with the end of excitement towards work, and the personality trait of adaptability is important in the progression of this situation (Çetin & Hazır, 2012: 74). As a result of studies (Deary et al., 1996; Süren et al., 2016; Bakker et al., 2006; Hochwalder, 2006; Düz, 2015; Muzika, 2019), a negative relationship has emerged between agreeableness and depersonalization dimension.

In addition, since harmonious individuals are in a managerial position in their working life and get successful results in their work (Tekin, 2012: 123), low sense of personal accomplishment feelings will be lower. Studies (Bakker et al., 2006; Süren et al., 2016) suggest that there is a negative relationship between agreeableness and low sense of personal accomplishment.

H2j: The agreeableness dimension of personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the dimension of emotional exhaustion.

H2k: The agreeableness dimension of personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the depersonalization dimension.

H2l: The agreeableness dimension of personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the low personal achievement dimension.

2.2.5. The Relationship Between Extraversion and Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Low Sense of Personal Accomplishment

Extroverted individuals adapt immediately to their environment and their communication with people is open (Haydaroğlu, 2020: 54). For this reason, they experience the feeling of burnout less than passive individuals with the communication they establish (Çiğşar, 2018: 17).

In studies (Francis et al., 2004; Burke et al., 2006; Ghorpade et al., 2007; Basım, et al., 2013; Düz, 2015; Süren et al., 2016; Muzika, 2019) extroversion revealed that individuals with a high score experience less emotional exhaustion. When it comes to depersonalization, studies (Zellars et al., 2000; Bakker et al., 2006; Kokkinos, 2007; Süren et al., 2016) show that individuals with extraversion will experience depersonalization less.

Allocating a social space for extroverted individuals (Tanar, 2020: 50) will reduce the low level of their personal accomplishment. Studies (Zellars et al., 2004; Bakker et al., 2006; Tanar, 2020) also support this idea by revealing that there is a negative and significant relationship between the two sub-dimensions.

H2m: The dimension of extraversion from personality

traits has a negative and significant effect on the dimension of emotional exhaustion.

H2n: The extraversion dimension of personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the depersonalization dimension.

H2o: The dimension of extraversion from personality traits has a negative and significant effect on the dimension of low sense of personal accomplishment.

2.3 Research Model and Hypotheses

In addition, the research model in line with the established hypotheses is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model

Source: own elaboration.

H1: Employees' personality traits have an effect on cyberloafing behaviors.

H2: Employees' personality traits have an effect on their burnout levels.

While the main hypotheses for the research are shown in Figure 1, the sub-hypotheses are supported by individual sources under the title of Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Purpose and Importance of the Research

Today, while the use of the internet provides an advantage for individuals, especially in terms of time, this can lead to loss of time at work and loss of productivity in business life (Dede, 2018: 3). Of course, there is a difference between individuals in the use of the internet for reasons other than work or non-educational reasons (Biçkes et al., 2018: 700).

In this case, personality traits come into play. Individuals who start their working life form an integrity against the organization and the social environment by determining their own personality roles from the first moment of this process (Örücü & Aksoy, 2018: 266). Many studies on personality traits have been found in the literature, and the fact that there is no similar research topic, especially within the scope of the tourism sector, reveals the originality and importance of the research.

For this reason, it is important to investigate which personality dimensions have an effect on cyberloafing

dimensions in the first part of the study. Another concept that can create serious risks when it occurs in the working life of the individual is burnout (Okutan, 2010: 132). While some individuals experience burnout in the face of situations in the work environment, some individuals can prevent burnout, and this is due to personality traits that differ in everyone (Gök, 2021: 1862).

Because of this situation, it is very important to investigate this issue in order to learn from which dimensions of the personality traits of the burnout feeling experienced by the employees in their work lives. For these reasons, this research; focuses on cyberloafing behavior and burnout levels of personality traits of hotel business employees.

3.2 Population and Sample

While determining the research universe, the facility list of İzmir Province Culture and Tourism Directorate was used (<http://izmir.ktb.gov.tr/>). The scope of the research was determined as 4 and 5 star hotels in Konak district. According to the list of facilities reached in Konak District, a total of 20 hotels with 4 and 5 stars were included in the research. Hotel establishments were called one by one and the number of personnel was requested, and a total of 1140 hotel employees were reached within this scope.

Of all the distributed face-to-face and online questionnaires, 370 questionnaires were returned as healthy. The sample size obtained as 370 is sufficient with 95% confidence (Kozak, 2018: 103). For the research, non-random sampling method, in which the population is determined by the researcher, was used (Haşiloğlu et al., 2015: 20). Since all hotel businesses in Turkey cannot be included in the research in terms of time and cost, it is limited to 4 and 5 star hotel businesses located in Konak district of İzmir. In addition, the research was limited to the personnel working between January 1 and April 22, 2022.

3.3 Data Collection Tool

In the research, a method called a structured question form or questionnaire was used, in which the researcher presented the questions he had previously designed for the subject he wanted to get information from to the target audience (Kozak, 2018: 59). A questionnaire consisting of 80-item statements was used in the study. In the first part of the questionnaire, the personality traits scale, which was developed by Psychologist O.P. John in 1990 and adapted into Turkish by Sümer & Sümer (2005), was used to measure the personality traits of employees. T

he personality traits scale consists of a 5-point Likert scale ("1=Totally Disagree" - "5=Totally Agree") and consists of 44 items. The scale has five dimensions (openness to experience, conscientiousness, neuroticism, agreeableness, and extroversion). The purpose of the second section of the questionnaire is to gauge the employees' habits of cyberloafing. The cyberloafing scale developed by Lim (2002), Blanchard & Henle (2008) and used by Örüçü & Yıldız (2014) in their studies was used. The cyberloafing scale also consists of a five-point Likert type scale ("1=Never" - "5=Always") and 14 items. In the third part of the questionnaire, a scale consisting of 22 items, which was

developed by Maslach and Jackson in 1981 and translated by Çetinkaya (2021), was used to measure the burnout levels of employees. The burnout levels scale also consists of 5-point Likert type ("1=Never", "- "5=Always") and 22 items. Finally, the fourth part of the questionnaire is about the demographic data of the participants.

4 FINDINGS

4.1 Analysis of Data

The data obtained in the research were analyzed using the SPSS (Static Packages for the Social Sciences) 26 program. Descriptive statistics, Factor Analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis were used in the study. Before starting the statistical analyzes to be made in the research, it is checked whether the data show a normal distribution (Karaatlı, 2014: 3). As a result of the normality test, since the skewness value is between -1,870 and 1,106 and the kurtosis value is between -1,248 and 3,390, it was determined that the data showed a normal distribution (Kim, 2013). For this reason, parametric tests were decided (Kozak, 2018: 139).

4.2. Findings on Demographic Characteristics

While 44.6% of the employees included in the research are female and 55.4% are male, it is seen that 50.5% of them are in the age group of 30 and below. 66.2% of the employees are single and 33.8% are married. It is seen that the monthly income of the participants is 4253.40 TL or less at the rate of 79.7%.

4.3 Findings Related to Factor Analysis and Reliability Analysis

According to the results of principal component analysis with varimax rotation applied in the factor analysis performed, significant results were obtained in all scales as a result of KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) sample adequacy and Bartlett's Sphericity Test values (Akgül & Çevik, 2003: 428; Kılıç, 2014: 44).

The KMO value for the personality traits scale is 0.798, the KMO value for the cyberloafing scale is 0.835, and the KMO value for the burnout level scale is 0.867. Bartlett test of sphericity p value of all scales is $p < 0.000$. Factor analysis was applied by determining the cut-off point of the factor load value as 0.40 (Şencan, 2005).

Overlapping items and items with a difference of less than 0.1 unit were excluded from the analysis, and factor analyzes were re-applied and their final form in Tables 2, 3, and 4 was given (Cokal, 2019: 1155). In addition, as a result of factor analysis, it is seen that the eigenvalues of the factors are significant because they have values greater than 1 (Zwick & Velicer, 1986).

It is seen that the dimension with the highest CA value for the reliability of the personality traits scale is openness to experience 0.900, and all other dimensions are reliable. CA values of cyberloafing scale; significant cyberloafing is 0.827, and insignificant cyberloafing is 0.777. In the burnout dimension, the CA value of the scale has the highest

emotional exhaustion of 0.911 and all other dimensions are reliable (Salvucci et al., 1997: 115).

According to Table 2, according to the level of agreement of the employees in the hotel business with the statements under the dimension of openness to experience, the expression "I am curious about many things" ($\bar{x}=4.337$), the expression "I am helpful" ($\bar{x}=4.362$) the most, the expression neuroticism the most In the dimension of "I can stay calm in tense situations and environments" ($\bar{x}=3.727$), the expression "I am an extroverted social person" ($\bar{x}=4.205$) the most in the dimension of Extraversion, and finally, "Lazy, among the expressions under the responsibility dimension" I tend to be inclined to be" ($\bar{x}=3.721$) statement.

According to Table 3, among the statements under the important cyberloafing behavior dimension according to the

participation levels of the hotel business employees, "I participate in social networks (Facebook, Twitter etc.) It is seen that they mostly agree with the statement "I do my banking transactions on the internet during working hours (such as EFT, money order)" ($\bar{x}=4.270$).

According to Table 4, among the expressions under the emotional exhaustion dimension of the hotel business employees, "I feel finished at the end of the working day" ($\bar{x}=2.700$), while in the low personal achievement dimension, "I don't really care what happens to some customers" ($\bar{x}=1.962$) It was determined that they mostly agreed with the statement "I deal with customers' problems very effectively" ($\bar{x}=4.275$) in the depersonalization dimension.

Table 2. Factor Analysis Results Regarding Personality Traits.

Factors		Fac.Loading	Eigenvalue	Explained variance(%)	$\bar{x}\alpha$	
Openness to Experience	I am original, I generate new ideas	,856	25,619	20,392	4,164	0,900
	My imagination is strong	,851			4,273	
	I'am creative	,827			4,048	
	I'm a smart, deep thinker	,827			4,256	
	Artistic and aesthetic things are important to me	,747			4,091	
	I like to play with ideas, to think about what they mean to me.	,734			4,108	
	I wonder many things	,698			4,337	
I am interested in art, music and literature.	,503	3,735				
Agreeableness	I am considerate and respectful to everyone	,815	12,692	11,993	4,254	0,825
	I like helping others	,775			4,345	
	I am helpful	,709			4,362	
	I am forgiving	,673			3,802	
	Sometimes I'm rude to other people	,669			3,956	
	Cold and indifferent to other people	,503			3,902	
Neuroticism	I am a worried person	,765	9,784	10,869	3,354	0,790
	I'm comfortable, I don't get stressed	,675			3,010	
	I can stay calm in tense situations	,658			3,727	
	I'm emotionally stable, it's easy					
	I wouldn't be unhappy	,639			3,162	
	I am pessimistic, sad person	,623			3,524	
	I get excited quickly	,595			2,840	
	My mood is variable	,557			2,908	
Extraversion	I'am silent	,845	7,415	10,654	3,573	0,832
	Sometimes I'm shy and shy	,767			3,445	
	I'm an introvert	,742			4,002	
	I am an extroverted social person	,576			4,205	
	I'm talkative	,574			3,940	
	I'm not shy, I'm sociable	,546			3,900	
Conscientiousness	I tend to be lazy	,772	6,154	7,755	3,721	0,684
	I'm a messy person, I'm not very organized	,760			3,618	
	I am easily distracted	,671			3,210	

*(Personality Traits Scale; Varimax Rotation Principal Components Analysis, Overall Reliability of the Scale: 0.856; Total Explained Variance: 61,663 %; KMO: 0.798; Bartlett Test of Sphericity X2: 6851,281; s.d.,435; p< 0.05).

Source: own elaboration.

Table 3. Factor Analysis Results on Cyberloafing.

Factors		Fac. Loading	Eigenvalue	Explained variance(%)	$\bar{x}$	
Serious Cyberloafing	I watch videos for entertainment purposes (like YouTube or zapkolik) on the internet during working hours.	,849		3,348		
	I visit virtual communities that have been created on the internet during working hours (such as sour dictionary)	,754		3,208		
	I play games for fun or to fill free time during working hours	,754	42,255	30,454	2,816	0,827
	I download music, videos, movies or documents over the internet during working hours	,717		3,532		
	I participate in social networks during working hours (Facebook, Twitter etc.)	,569		3,632		
	I read blogs during working hours (a platform for free communication between the author and the reader)	,558		3,167		
Minor Cyberloafing	I visit news sites on the internet during working hours (newspapers, online news TVs and other news sites)	,787		3,856		
	I do operations such as receiving, sending or checking e-mails for non-business communication during working hours.	,747		3,673		
	I do my banking transactions over the internet during working hours (such as EFT, Money Order transactions)	,712	14,115	25,916	4,270	0,777
	I shop online for personal products during working hours.	,705		3,800		
	I visit investment-related websites during working hours (such as finance, stock market sites)	,547		2,873		

** (Cyberloafing Scale; Principal Component Analysis with Varimax Rotation, Overall Reliability of the Scale: 0.859; Total Variance Explained: 56.370%; KMO: 0.835; Bartlett Test of Sphericity X2 : 1694,148; p.d.: 55; p< 0.05).
Source: own elaboration.

Table 4. Factor Analysis Results Regarding Burnout Levels.

Factors		Fac. Loading	Eigenvalue	Explained variance(%)	$\bar{x}$	
Emotional	I feel tired when I wake up in the morning and have to spend another day at work	,874		2,405		
	I feel emotionally drained at my job.	,866		2,381		
Exhaustion	I feel finished at the end of the workday	,819	43,161	34,120	2,700	0,911
	I feel frustrated by my job	,808		2,102		
	Working directly with people puts too much stress	,785		2,391		
	I feel so energetic	,644		2,310		
	I'm worried this job is straining me emotionally	,589		2,437		
	Low Sense of Personal Accomplishment	I feel like I treat some customers as if they are objects and not people	,848	14,472	19,512	
I really don't care what happens to some customers.		,842		1,962		
Since I started this job, I have become desensitized to people.		,766		1,827		
	I can easily understand how customers feel about something	,800	10,838	14,830	4,191	0,671
	I deal with customers' problems very effectively	,785		4,275		
	I feel good after a busy day with my clients	,741		3,802		

*** (Burnout Levels Scale; Principal Component Analysis with Varimax Rotation, Overall Reliability of the Scale: 0.852; Total Variance Explained: 68.470%; KMO: 0.867; Bartlett Test of Sphericity X2: 2676,225; p.d.: 78; p< 0.05).
Source: own elaboration.

4.4. Regression Analysis Findings on the Effects of Personality Traits on Cyberloafing Behavior and Burnout Levels

To ascertain whether personality traits, the independent variable, have an impact on the dependent variables, cyberloafing behavior and burnout levels, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted. According to Multiple Linear Regression analysis of the effect of personality traits on significant cyberloafing, openness to experience (β : -0.072, p:0.173>0.05) and conscientiousness (β : -0.034, p: 0.494>0.05) variables were found to be significant cyberloafing. It is seen that there is no negative and significant effect on the behavior.

In this direction, the variables that were found to be meaningless were removed from the analysis and the analysis was repeated, and the following results were obtained.

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Personality Traits	Serious Cyberloafing		
	B	t	Sig.
Constant		13,072	0,000
Neuroticism	0,273	5,622	0,000
Agreeableness	-0,225	-4,280	0,000
Extraversion	0,337	6,417	0,000

(F: 24,617; P : 0,000; R: 0,410; R2 0,168; Adjusted Coeff. Deter.R2 0,161; StandardDeviation: 0, 66336; ; P<0,05).

Source: own elaboration.

When Table: 6 is examined, the results of multiple linear regression analysis are statistically significant (F: 24,617, P: 0.000<0.05). According to the results of the analysis, the R2 value is 0.168. According to this value, it is seen that the 16.8% variance in significant cyberloafing behavior depends on personality traits. According to the results of the analysis, neuroticism (β : 0.273, p:0.000<0.05) and extraversion (β : 0.337, p:0.000<0.05) variables were positively correlated on significant cyberloafing behavior (β : -0.225, p:0.000<0.05) is also an independent variable with a significant negative effect.

As a result, according to the multiple linear regression analysis, among the hypotheses put forward within the scope of the research; findings of rejection of H1a and H1c hypotheses and acceptance of H1e, H1g, H1i hypotheses were reached.

According to the multiple linear regression analysis, openness to experience, (β : -0.042, p: 0.448 > 0.05) and neuroticism (β : -0.025, p: 0.642 > 0.05) as independent variables were found to be negative, while coherence (β : 0,18, p: 0,753 > 0,05) has been concluded that there is no serious positive effect on the minor cyberloafing behavior. In this direction, the variables that were found to be meaningless were removed from the analysis and the analysis was repeated, and the following results were obtained.

Table 8. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Personality Traits	Minor Cyberloafing		
	B	t	Sig.
Constant		8,933	0,000
Extraversion	0,258	5,156	0,000
Conscientiousness	-0,120	-2,406	0,017

(F: 16,275; P : 0,000; R: 0,285; R2 : 0,081; Adjusted Coeff. Deter. R2 : 0,076; Standard Deviation: 0,62388; ; P<0,05).

Source: own elaboration.

When Table: 8 is examined, the results of multiple linear regression analysis are statistically significant (F: 16,275, P: 0.000<0.05). According to the results of the analysis, the R2 value is 0.081. According to this value, it is seen that the 8.1% variance in significant cyberloafing behavior depends on personality traits. According to the results of the analysis, the variable of extraversion (β : 0.258, p:0.000<0.05) has a positive effect on the serious cyberloafing behavior, while the variable of conscientiousness (β : -0.120, p: 0.017<0.05) has a negative effect on the serious cyberloafing behavior.

As a result, according to the multiple linear regression analysis, among the hypotheses put forward within the scope of the research; findings of rejection of H1b, H1f, H1h hypotheses and acceptance of H1d and H1j hypotheses were reached.

According to multiple linear regression analysis, it is seen that openness to experience (β : -0.042, p: 0.413 > 0.05) and agreeableness (β : -0.071, p: 0.191 > 0.05) variables are not negative and significant on emotional exhaustion. . In this direction, the variables that were found to be meaningless were removed from the analysis and the analysis was repeated, and the following results were obtained.

Table 10. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results.

Personality Traits	Burn Out		
	B	t	Sig.
Constant		17,304	0,000
Conscientiousness	-0,148	-3,074	0,002
Neuroticism	0,344	7,029	0,000
Extraversion	-0,156	-3,319	0,001

(F: 32,258; P : 0,000; R: 0,457; R2 : 0,209; Adjusted Coeff. Deter. R2 : 0,209; Standard Deviation: 0, 64023; ; P<0,05).

Source: own elaboration.

The results of multiple linear regression analysis when Table 10 were examined were statistically significant (F: 32,258, P: 0.000 < 0.05). According to the results of the analysis, the R2 value is 0.209. According to this value, 20.9% of the variance of the emotional exhaustion sub-dimension is related to personality traits.

According to the results of the analysis, while the variables of conscientiousness (β : -0.148, p: 0.002<0.05) and extraversion (β : -0.156, p: 0.001<0.05) are negative on emotional exhaustion, the variable of neuroticism (β : 0.344, p: 0.000<0.05), it was found to have a significant positive effect. As a result, according to the multiple linear regression analysis, among the hypotheses put forward within the scope of the research; The findings of rejecting the H2a and H2j hypotheses and accepting the H2d, H2g and H2m hypotheses were reached.

According to the multiple linear regression analysis, while the independent variables were responsible (β : 0.93, p: 0.055 > 0.05) and agreeableness (β : 0.097, p: 0.074 > 0.05) variables were positive on depersonalization, neuroticism (β : -0.065, p: 0.185 > 0.05) variable is negative and not significant. In this direction, the variables that were found to be meaningless were removed from the analysis and the analysis was repeated, and the following results were obtained.

Table 12. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results.

Personality Traits	Depersonalization		
	B	t	Sig.
Constant		11,447	0,000
Openness to Experience	-0,222	-4,542	0,000
Extraversion	-0,327	-6,713	0,000

(F: 45,152; P : 0,000; R: 0,444; R2 : 0,197; Adjusted Coeff. Deter. R2 : 0,193; Standard Deviation: 0, 56739; P<0,05).

Source: own elaboration.

When Table 12 is examined, the results of multiple linear regression analysis are statistically significant (F: 45,152, P: 0.000<0.05). According to the results of the analysis, the R2 value is 0.197. According to this value, 19.7% of the variance in the depersonalization sub-dimension appears to depend on personality traits.

According to the analysis results, openness to experience (β : -0.222, p: 0.000<0.05) and extraversion (β : -0.327, p: 0.000<0.05) variables were found to have a negative and significant effect on depersonalization. As a result, according to the multiple linear regression analysis, among the hypotheses put forward within the scope of the research; Findings of rejection of H2e, H2h, H2k hypotheses and acceptance of H2b and H2n hypotheses were reached.

According to the multiple linear regression analysis, openness to experience (β : 0.93, p : 0.791 > 0.05) among the independent variables was positively related to low sense of personal accomplishment, conscientiousness (β :-0.049, p : 0.357 > 0.05), neuroticism. (β : -0.047, p : 0.383 > 0.05) and extraversion (β : -0.068, p : 0.227 > 0.05) variables were found to be negative and not significant on depersonalization. In this direction, the variables that were found to be meaningless were removed from the analysis and the analysis was repeated, and the following results were obtained.

Table 14: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Personality Traits	Low Sense of Personal Accomplishment		
	B	t	Sig.
Constant		11,296	
Agreeableness	-0,237	-4,670	0,000

(F: 21,810; P : 0,000; R: 0,237; R2 : 0,056; Adjusted Coeff. Deter. R2 : 0,053; Standard Deviation: 0, 67030; ; P<0,05).

Source: own elaboration.

When Table 14 are examined, the results of multiple linear regression analysis are statistically significant (F: 21,810, P: 0.000<0.05). According to the results of the analysis, the R2 value is 0.056. According to this value, it is seen that the 5.6% variance in the low sense of personal accomplishment variable depends on the personality traits. According to the results of the analysis, it is seen that the variable of agreeableness (β : -0.237, p : 0.000<0.05) has a negative and significant effect on low sense of personal accomplishment.

As a result, according to the multiple linear regression analysis, among the hypotheses put forward within the scope of the research; The findings of rejecting the H2c, H2f, H2i and H2o hypotheses and accepting the H21 hypothesis were reached.

5 CONCLUSIONAND SUGGESTIONS

Hotel businesses serve as a mirror for Turkey's tourism revenues. A qualified, responsible and addiction-free staff always creates positive perceptions in the eyes of consumers (Dedeoğlu et al., 2018). In particular, the employees of the hotel businesses are the pioneers in terms of marketing the service. For this reason, today's technological addictions can become a threat to hotel businesses when they enter the working hours of the employees.

As a result of the literature review, it was learned that the main element of cyberloafing behavior, which has become a threat to employees, is personality traits. Another factor that threatens the services of hotel businesses is the burnout syndrome experienced by their employees. This syndrome causes macro damage to the managers, colleagues, environment and especially the individual himself in the business life of individuals (Okutan, 2010: 193).

Personality traits are the most important reason why hotel businesses, which are of great importance for the tourism sector, experience burnout for their employees. Personality traits determine the level of prevention of burnout syndrome (Sarıkaya, 2007: 3). For these reasons, the purpose of this research was to investigate how hotel

employees' personality qualities affect their cyberloafing behavior and levels of burnout. In line with the findings of the research, the most important and striking results are given below;

- When the effect of personality traits on significant cyberloafing behavior was examined, it was seen that neuroticism, agreeableness and extraversion dimensions had a significant effect. It has been determined that the most influential dimension of personality traits on significant cyberloafing behavior is extroversion. In studies measuring the effect of personality traits on significant cyberloafing behavior (Krishnan et al., 2010; Jia et al., 2013; Andreassen et al., 2014; Örüçü & Aksoy, 2017; Varghese & Barber, 2017) It was concluded that there was a positive and significant effect on behavior. Many reasons can be counted, such as the fact that the extraversion dimension has a positive and significant effect on significant cyberloafing behavior, that these individuals are open to innovation, that they are energetic and curious, and that they are dissatisfied. The most distinctive feature of extroverted individuals is their social nature. For this reason, they may not want to break away from their social circle and friends even during working hours.

- When the effect of personality traits on insignificant cyberloafing behavior was examined, it was determined that the most influential variable was extroversion, and then the conscientiousness dimension emerged. In the studies of Çivilidağ (2016), Örüçü & Aksoy (2018), which examined the effect of personality traits on minor cyberloafing behavior, it was revealed that the variable of extraversion has a positive and significant effect on minor cyberloafing behavior. It can be argued that the fact that the extraversion dimension has a positive and significant effect on the insignificant cyberloafing behavior is that these individuals are social people who are open to communication. Due to the fact that extroverted employees are in constant interaction with the external environment, they can engage in unimportant cyberloafing activities such as receiving personal e-mails and browsing news sites during working hours. Conscientiousness is the other independent variable that has a negative and significant effect on minor cyberloafing behavior. Lim, (2002), Tan and Demir, (2018), Jia, Jia and Karau (2013), O'Neill, Hambley and Bercovich (2014), Varghese and Barber (2017), in which the effect of the conscientiousness variable on minor cyberloafing behavior was examined, In Dede's (2018) studies, it was concluded that the variable of conscientiousness has a negative and significant effect on minor cyberloafing behavior. Employees with a dominant responsibility feature will be aware of the work they will do and will show disciplined work, so their tendency to show minor cyberloafing behavior will decrease.

- Another important result as a result of the analyzes is that the variable that causes the most effect on emotional exhaustion from personality traits is the neuroticism variable. In studies measuring the effect of personality traits on emotional exhaustion (Deary et al., 1996; Zellars et al., 2000; Bühler & Land, 2003; Kim et al., 2009; Tanar, 2020; Süren, 2015), neuroticism has a positive effect on emotional exhaustion. was found to have a significant effect. Neurotic workers may experience emotional exhaustion as a result of constant anxiety, insecurity and not being able to focus on

the given job sufficiently. Jobs given by managers can become overwhelming for neurotic employees and their anxiety can result in emotional exhaustion.

- It has been determined that the variable of openness to experience from personality traits has the most effect on depersonalization. In studies (Bakker et al., 2006; Okutan, 2010; Zellars, Perrew & Hochwarter, 2000; Süren et al., 2016; Muzika, 2019) it was concluded that the variable of openness to experience has a negative and significant effect on depersonalization. Since employees who are open to experience are individuals who live their emotions actively and are curious, it is very difficult for them to become detached from their own self, such as depersonalization. Employees who are open to experience want to experience all kinds of innovations in their working life and are not expected to be insensitive to opportunities that come their way.

- As a result of the regression analysis conducted on the effect of personality traits on low sense of personal accomplishment, it was determined that openness to experience had a positive effect, while neuroticism, conscientiousness and extraversion had no negative and significant effect on low sense of personal accomplishment. In the study of Düz (2015), it was determined that the variable of openness to experience did not have an effect on low sense of personal accomplishment, and in the study of Yüksel (2017), the variables of neuroticism and extraversion did not have an effect on low sense of personal accomplishment.

In line with the results obtained, various suggestions were presented to new researchers and the hotel industry regarding the effects of personality traits on cyberloafing behavior and burnout levels.

Suggestions to researchers;

- Future research may do the research on different samples or on different departments at the hotel (housekeeping, front desk, etc.).

- Future research may examine the relationship between the variables used in this study and demographic variables, or may also take into account the length of service of the employees.

- Future research may examine the relationship between cyberloafing behavior and burnout levels. In addition, it can be examined whether personality traits have a mediating effect on these two variables.

- Future research may examine the effects of personality traits on cyberloafing behavior and burnout levels in different sectors. In this way, inter-sectoral comparisons can be made.

Recommendations for hotel industry managers;

- Hotel management managers may limit the devices that employees can access the internet in order to prevent cyberloafing behavior.

- Training can be given to hotel business employees in areas such as mobile device usage and labor law.

- Cyberloafing behavior can be reduced by giving responsibilities to hotel business employees in order not to be idle during working hours.

- Protocols prepared for the use of internet by hotel employees can be signed. Those who do not comply with the protocols can be penalized.

- Due to the intense work schedule of hotel business employees, areas where employees can use personal internet can be created during the hours determined by the managers.

- According to the results of the research, since there is a positive relationship between neuroticism and extraversion variables and serious cyberloafing behavior, human resources managers can specifically eliminate neurotic individuals by applying the "Personality Inventory Test" in recruitment. Thus, it can prevent problems such as low service quality and employee turnover that may arise in the workplace.

- Due to the negative relationship between the adaptability variable and serious cyberloafing behavior, priority may be given to compatible individuals during recruitment.

- In the recruitment process in hotels, it would be more appropriate to give priority to extroverted and responsible job candidates among job candidates, since the variable of extraversion has positive results on minor cyberloafing behavior and conscientiousness negatively. Thanks to extroverted and responsible employees, businesses can achieve more success.

- The hotel management should give more importance to the employees' coping with burnout, and raise their welfare level by taking their wishes and needs seriously. Because if the internal customer is positively satisfied, the sense of loyalty will increase, the turnover rate will decrease and the external customer satisfaction will also increase.

- In order to minimize burnout, employees can be given training on stress management.

- Organizing the working environments of the employees in a way that motivates them can reduce the factors that increase burnout.

- In order to reduce the burnout levels of the employees, the promises (salary, working conditions, etc.) in their recruitment should be transparent.

- Hotel management managers should be able to set fixed days and create an environment for discussion with employees, self-sacrificing work should be rewarded and motivating environments should be created. All of these elements can increase the self-confidence of employees and prevent burnout.

- The study's conclusions showed that extraversion, emotional exhaustion, and conscientiousness were negatively correlated. For this reason, HR managers can identify responsible and extroverted individuals by applying tests to measure personality types in terms of time and cost in recruitment.

- Since the variables of openness to experience and extraversion have a negative effect on depersonalization, it is seen that those who are open to experience and extrovert will behave less insensitively in their work life. Especially since there is a lot of face-to-face communication with guests in hotel businesses, the fact that employees are open to experience and extrovert will increase the quality of the person-customer relationship to be established. In addition, individuals who are open to experience and extrovert can work in departments that are strong in terms of communication such as front office, public relations, human resources and marketing.

• Consistency variable also has a negative effect on low sense of personal accomplishment; They will focus on success rather than failure, with the motivation they see from their managers, as a result of harmonious employees fulfilling the given task, reliable and working in harmony with their colleagues. The productivity of compatible individuals who realize that they are successful is higher than other individuals.

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Final table. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	60	40
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	60	40
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	60	40
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	60	40
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	60	40
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	60	40
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	60	40
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	60	40
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	60	40
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or postpublication stages	60	40
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	60	40
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	60	40
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	60	40
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	60	40

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